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Advanced Technology Filtration For A Better Crew And Passenger Experience

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Abstract

Cabin air on commercial aircraft today is typically supplied by bleed air systems from engines or APU's or ram air. This input air contains contamination, which may include hydraulic fluids, engine oils, pyrolysis products, multiple types of volatile organic compounds (VOC's), ozone and particulates. For the safety and well-being of crews and passengers, removal of these type of these contaminants as well as odors from bleed air and/or re-circulated air is essential to improve cabin air quality. Thinking of air quality as a matter of safety, as opposed to simply comfort, has dramatically changed the way that airlines make decisions regarding the products and services used to attain clean air in the cabin of the aircraft. This is even more important today as we work to provide a safe cabin environment to remove bacteria and viruses. Airlines, OEM's and the traveling public are just now starting to realize how important cabin air quality is to the aviation industry. PTI Technologies has been investing in advanced designs and new technology to meet this need, and has been testing this against existing industry standards. Our presentation will share the results of this work and how it can positively impact the commercial aviation industry by providing quality cabin air for a better crew and passenger experience.

Keywords

PTI, PTI Technologies, cabin air, bleed air, contamination, VOC, particulates, ozone, safety, cabin, environment

1 Introduction

The cabin air on commercial aircraft today is typically supplied by two sources – 50% from recirculated air and 50% by bleed air taken from the compressor section of the engines or APU's. The one exception today is the 787, which uses compressed ram air. The 50% of the cabin air that comes from the bleed air contains contamination, which may include hydraulic fluids, engine oils, pyrolysis products, multiple types of volatile organic compounds and particulates, as well as ozone. For the health, safety and well-being of crews and passengers, removal of these type of contaminants

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as well as odors from bleed air and/or re-circulated air is essential to improve cabin air quality. Thinking of air quality as a matter of flight safety and health, as opposed to simply comfort, has dramatically changed the way that airlines make decisions regarding the products and services used to attain clean air in the cabin of the aircraft. This is even more important today as we work to provide a safe cabin environment to remove bacteria and viruses. Airlines, OEM's, regulators and the traveling public are just now starting to realize how important cabin air quality is to the aviation industry.

PTI first successfully applied cabin air filtration technology in 1989 on the B-2 program, and this has continued in a number of other military and manned space programs. During this time, PTI's engineering team has invested in the development of special filter media by collaborating with media companies to meet our customer's challenging requirements and specifications. These applications required custom IP adsorbents to capture gases such as:

- Ammonia
- Phenol
- Indole
- Skatole
- Butyric acid
- Methyl Mercaptan
- Hydrogen Sulphide

PTI's development of cabin air filters for military program has required development of special custom adsorbents to capture Chemical War Agents (CWA) to protect cabin air including:

- VX gas
- Soman gas
- Mustard gas

PTI's integration of advanced integrated HEPA technology with adsorbents impregnated proprietary media technology is used today to meet performance requirements of military and manned space cabin air filtration applications. In addition, PTI's newest CabinSafe® HEPA technology has been in service since 2012 with global airlines for the recirculation air loop on a number of Boeing and Airbus commercial aircraft. For bleed air applications, PTI has designed, manufactured and supported APU bleed air removing liquids and particulates on a number of engine applications for P&W, Honeywell, Lockheed, Rolls-Royce, Airbus, Embraer and military customers.

Over the last few years based on customer inputs, PTI Technologies began investing in advanced filter designs and new technology to meet customer needs in providing a higher level of filtration for Fuel Tank Inerting Systems (FTIS) to extend the life of the air separation modules. PTI engineering team has now developed patented integrated FTIS filtration designs, which offer improved performance in capturing aerosols (liquid and particulates), Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC's) and other contaminants as well as providing ozone conversion. PTI has manufactured these FTIS filter designs and tested them in-house and at independent third party laboratories to EN and ISO standards and the results, show significant promise for improved filtration performance as discussed below. During this technology development and test programs, PTI also began to understand that this technology was directly applicable to the challenge of filtering the bleed air portion of aircraft cabin air.

This technical paper will show PTI's design approach and results of our work on this integrated filtration technology and how it can positively impact the commercial aviation industry by providing quality cabin air for a safer and more healthy environment in the aircraft as well as a better crew and passenger experience. This paper will also focus on how cabin air filters affect the quality of cabin air and how air filters can be used to limit crew and passenger exposure to aerosols, VOC's, contaminants and ozone. It will also cover filter efficiency and explain why PTI is recommending certain levels of filtration to achieve optimum results.

2 Background

Aircraft cabin air quality and safety has never been under such a strong public focus as it is today, during the COVID-19 pandemic, especially given strong evidence that these viruses can spread as aerosols through the air. However, in reality, the subject of aircraft cabin air quality has been a topic of discussion in the industry since the 1950's when Boeing first recognized the need for filtration, but did not have the filtration technology to answer the problem. Although we have evolved technology and slowly brought HEPA filtration to commercial aircraft today, it has only been a partial answer. Within the industry, there have been a number of issues and incidents where cabin air quality has affected the health of crew, flight safety from the incapacitation of crew, as well as negative effects on passengers.

In doing design of filters to address cabin air quality, there are many factors to consider. Aerosols are so small that buoyant forces overcome gravity, allowing them to stay suspended in the air for long periods, or they evaporate before they hit the floor, leaving the solid particulate ("droplet nuclei") free to float very long distances, causing what we often refer to as "airborne" transmission. There is growing evidence that in addition to contact and droplet spread, the transmission of aerosols is plausible under favorable conditions, particularly in relatively confined settings with poor ventilation and long duration exposure to high concentrations of aerosols. As we address viruses, the virus may attach to smaller or larger particles (solid or liquid), so a wide range of particle sizes have to be considered from some micrometers down to the nanoscale. PTI's advanced filter technology was developed to remove aerosols and virus carrying particles to improve cabin air quality.

Bleed air is outside air and in theory it should be fresh and clean. However as it passes through the compressor section of the engines or APU, it becomes contaminated with aerosol droplets or vapors of engine oil, hydraulic fluids, other organic or inorganic compounds, carbon dioxide or other by-products of combustion as they enter the aircraft. The recirculated portion of cabin air is not fresh and given the potentially large numbers of passengers on an aircraft, there are high concentrations of particulates. These particulates include fibers, dust, skin particles, bacteria (up to 30,000 bacterial organisms per minute per passenger could be released into the cabin environment), as well as odors in the air inside an aircraft. Bacteria thrive in high humidity, and viruses thrive in low humidity - both conditions can be found on commercial aircraft. All of these contaminants are all a potential risk to crews and passengers.

If we think of cabin air quality as a matter of flight safety and health, as opposed to simply passenger comfort, it dramatically changes the way that consumers make decisions regarding the products and services used to attain clean air. Using an air filter with a higher Minimum Efficiency Reporting Value (MERV) rating than what a system is designed for, can actually impair its performance. The smaller pores in more highly rated air filters create resistance to air flow, can lower the system's efficiency and put strain on the overall system.

Cabin air contamination comes in two different forms:

1. **Solid particulates** (dust, pollen, smoke particles, dust mites). HEPA filters are used to filter solid particulates out mechanically.
2. **Gaseous air pollutants** (odors, smells, VOCs, cigarette smoke smell, kitchen oil smell, etc.). The job of removing this falls on the activated adsorbent portion of an air filter.

The combination of HEPA filters and activated adsorbent filters working in tandem is needed to solve the complex problem of cabin air quality - they are the two most important air purifier filters.

Odors, smells, and Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC's) just pass through HEPA filter media as they are gases - a mechanical barrier does not stop them. Rather, a process of adsorption to an activated adsorbent material stops them. During the adsorption process, the gas molecules adhere to a solid surface of adsorbents. PTI filters technology addresses this issue by using advanced integrated HEPA technology, which integrates HEPA filters with adsorbent impregnated proprietary media technology.

3 PTI Advanced Integrated HEPA Technology

PTI's current in-service cabin air filters are High Efficiency Particulate Air (HEPA) filters and are manufactured using recommended practices as published in Environmental Technologies, not ASHRAE.

PTI advanced integrated HEPA technology filters improves air quality by adding new technology to reduce VOC's, minimizing adverse health effects such as headaches, nausea and nose/throat irritation or discomfort. Our integrated HEPA technology filters also reduce severe odor incidents thereby reducing unscheduled maintenance and repairs and keeping flights on schedule. These filters were developed with extensive work conducted by PTI's Engineering team in partnership with media manufacturers and OEM's. Tests conducted by independent labs have shown that CabinSafe® advanced integrated HEPA filters with ozone catalytic converters can reduce VOC's and ozone concentrations in the cabin thus keeping a healthy cabin air quality for the crew and passengers. These filters are engineered with a multi-layer media enabling to trap the dirt and large particles before the air reaches the final filters downstream, which then remove the smaller particles. This multi-filter system extends the life of the filters, leading to overall cost savings. PTI advanced integrated HEPA technology filters can perform better for same basis weight and pressure drop as other filters in the market.

3.1 Performance Test Data For Integrated Filter Elements

PTI advanced integrated HEPA technology filters were tested per EN 4618. **Figure 1** shows the aerosol (liquids and particulates) efficiency versus particle size.

Figure 1 Aerosol efficiency versus particle diameter.

The filter element was then tested against single challenge gases per EN 4618. The first challenge gas was formaldehyde:

- Air Flow Rate: 45.75 cfm (3.5 lbs/min)
- Upstream Concentration: 38 ppb
- Temperature: 160 °F (71 °C)

The results of this testing are show in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2 Adsorption curve: Efficiency versus time.

PTI's integrated filter element was also subjected to ozone testing to determine performance of the new catalytic converter technology being used. This test was to determine both efficiency of the converter and performance at various temperatures. The test was performed at:

- Air Flow Rate: 58.8 cfm (4.5 lbs/min)
- Upstream Concentration: 9.5 ppm
- Temperature: 160 °F (71 °C)

The results of these tests are shown in [Figure 3](#) and [Figure 4](#).

Figure 3 Adsorption curve: Efficiency versus time.

Figure 4 Efficiency versus temperature.

The filter element was tested against a mix of five challenge gases per EN 4618. The gas mixture was Butane, Formaldehyde, Naphthalene, Toluene and Ozone. The test conditions were:

- Air Flow Rate: 45.75 cfm (3.5 lbs/min)
- Upstream Concentration: 13 ppm
- Temperature: 72.3 °F (22.4 °C)

The test results are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Adsorption curve: Efficiency versus time.

4 Conclusions

- PTI offers advanced HEPA filter technology best integrated solution for the removal of aerosol, air particulates and VOC reduction including ozone.

- PTI's Integrated Filter Modular Design
 1. Used as a cabin air filter will eliminate adverse health effects for crew and passengers, or if used in a FTIS application, increase protection for the Air Separation Module (ASM).
 2. Provides low pressure drop.
 3. Keeps energy costs low and can be easily adapted for use in existing air systems.
 4. Lightweight and long life.
 5. Ensures economical operating costs.

About the Authors

Kanwar Suri holds a MS (Engineering) and DER FAA certification for PTI Technologies. He is the Senior Vice President of Engineering with over 35 years' experience in hydraulic and filtration industry. He was a chairman of Vice Chairman of SAE Contamination Committee and Secretary of NFPA Committee. He is actively involved in several SAE & NFPA technical committees and guides them to develop industry standards, has written and presented technical papers to INDA and FILTECH filtration conferences and holds several US patents in the field of hydraulic filtration and pressure sensing devices.

Michael Gao received his B.E. and M.E. degree in Mechanical Engineering from Zhejiang University, Hangzhou, People's Republic of China in 1989 and M.S. degree in Engineering Mathematics from Claremont Graduate University, Claremont, California in 1996. From 1996 to 2000, he was a Design Engineer; Project Engineer with Western Filter Corp. (now Donaldson). Since 2001, he has been a Sr. Design Engineer, Sr. Project Engineer, Engineering Manager and the current position of Director of Engineering with PTI Technologies Inc. He is a voting committee member of SAE A-6C1 Contamination & Filtration Group, SAE AE-5D Fuel Tank Flammability Reduction Systems Group and has authored numerous SAE documents for publications. Mr. Gao holds four US Patents and is an expert in the aerospace filtration industry.

David Conrad received the B.S. degree in Chemical and Petroleum Refining Engineering from the Colorado School of Mines, Golden, Colorado in 1979. Currently, he is the Vice President, Business Development at PTI Technologies based in Oxnard, California. Before joining PTI, he was with Zodiac Water & Waste Aero Systems as Vice President, Sales Marketing and Customer Service. He spent three years as the Director International Sales & Marketing of Guangzhou Aircraft Maintenance and Engineering Co., Ltd (GAMECO) in Guangzhou, People's Republic of China. He has also served as the Vice President, Sales, Marketing and Customer Service as well as General Manager, PSI at Rexnord Aerospace, as well as positions with Goodrich Cargo Systems (based in Beijing, China), and AeroUnion Corporation. He began his career progressing through a number of business development and leadership positions in Honeywell/ AlliedSignal. Mr. Conrad holds one US Patent.